

Last-mile delivery through electric motorbikes: Modelling considerations for parcel vs. food delivery

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Abstract. The use of electric motorbikes for last-mile delivery fills a gap between electric cargo-bikes and electric vans in cities, suburban and rural areas. Planning and sizing the use of electric motorbikes for delivery poses several challenges to meeting fleet managers' eco-efficiency and cost-effectiveness objectives while maintaining high levels of customer satisfaction. Consolidating deliveries and using optimised routes helps reduce consumption and reduce the overall footprint. In this paper, we address and describe modelling considerations that are significant for planning delivery services using electric motorbikes: battery consumption and route planning. We address these modelling considerations differentiating particularities between parcel and food delivery. The two approaches share multiple similarities but they face variances regarding customer demand and delivery procedures.

Keywords: goods delivery, modelling, electric motorbikes

1 Introduction

The adoption of electric vehicles for shared urban mobility and last-mile goods delivery is increasing mainly pushed forward by the need to reduce the environmental impact in the cities. In particular, electric motorbikes (also known as E2W) are two-wheeled vehicles powered by electricity instead of traditional internal combustion engines. They are relatively lightweight vehicles and take up little parking space. Thus, the use of these types of vehicles for last-mile delivery fills a gap between electric cargo-bikes and electric vans, valid not only in cities but also being able to reach suburban and rural areas (less accessible for bikes) with ease.

However, fleet owners face several challenges. Data-driven simulation and planning technologies, based for instance on Digital Twins (DT), are emerging as valuable tools for the assessment of initial investment and monitoring of fleet operations. Model-based DT and Data-driven DT (without explicit knowledge of the physical behaviour), while some authors also refer to Hybrid DT. Some works

conclude by stating the superiority of data-driven solutions over model-based ones due to their ability to handle systems with high complexity [2]. Applications for transportation and, more concretely, electromobility, the behaviour of the electric vehicles and real-time battery management have been addressed in the literature [2], [3], [1]. Even though some works address design optimisation as one of the purposes of using DTs [2], they are applied from the vehicle design perspective. Nevertheless, literature focused on electric motorbikes is limited and the availability of data able to support comprehensive and detailed studies is lacking.

In this context, this paper aims to describe the lessons learnt during our process of building delivery demand estimation and motorbike battery consumption estimation models and the main considerations to be addressed before tackling the development of fleet and charging station planning solutions for goods delivery. To the authors' knowledge, no works have addressed modelling last-mile goods delivery services using electric motorbikes based on real data. This paper wants to contribute towards this direction.

2 Problem statement

Building planning software to help dimension the use of electric motorbikes to serve goods delivery in the last mile requires modelling the trips that will be required and the estimated energy consumption pattern of the fleet. A data-driven approach based on machine learning models is proposed, using real current motorbike trips (electric and conventional) of goods and parcel delivery services in multiple European cities.

The final objective of these models will be to be able to determine the demand of requests from each geographical region at a given time frame, including cities currently covered by the delivery services and new cities where future service deployments are being planned, and to what extent this demand can be satisfied by a fleet of E2Ws of a given size.

2.1 Study of available information

Real data from delivery companies is the main source for training machine learning algorithms to build electric motorbike battery behaviour models and to build demand prediction models for parcel and food delivery services, named HDPE (Home Delivery Parcel Electric) and HDFE (Home Delivery Food Electric).

The information consists of tracks with geolocated positions every few seconds and battery State-of-Charge (SoC) value every few seconds. A track begins when the engine is started and it ends when stopped, in addition, stops during the track are identified.

2.2 Auxiliary data

In order to build a solution as generic as possible, the following well-known existing socio-economic city indicators and geographical zoning scheme data sources have been identified.

- City cartography source: OpenStreetMap [4] to build the transportation network and open data Digital Terrain Model for the elevation.
- Geographical zoning source based on census sections.
- Socio-economic indicators for each section such as: Population, Average age, Percentage of population with higher education over the population aged 16 or over, Percentage of people over 64 years of age, Percentage of people between 16 and 64 years of age, Percentage of foreign population, Average level of studies, Percentage of active population over population aged 16 or over, Average household income.

Socio-economic indicators are useful to characterise the type of end-users that are served by the E2W fleet in the delivery area, affecting the demand. Moreover, city cartography and zoning data are useful for determining the layout of the transportation network and the geographical extension covered by the E2W fleet, affecting the service operation (deliveries according to travelled distance, e.g.). They are key to plan and size fleets for delivery services in new locations.

3 Methodology

3.1 Initial exploratory analysis and cleaning

The route duration of the tracks using the timestamp of the origin and destination was calculated as a first step. Some differences in the average duration of the route between food and parcel delivery were found and multiple outliers were also identified, since, for example, the duration of some journeys was greater than a whole day. Before cleaning measurements that fall out of quartiles, it was noticed that the tracks existing in the dataset did not homogeneously reflect journeys from depot to depot because the behaviour of all drivers was not consistent. In some cases, the motorbike engine is not stopped when it returns to the depot, and in some delivery stops, the engine may or may not be stopped, representing a new track beginning. An example can be seen in Figure 1. This has required a process to clean and process the tracks into a new entity called "trip", where each trip must begin and end in a depot.

3.2 Depot detection

This process identifies depot locations since this information was not included in the dataset. A density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN) algorithm, which is an unsupervised density-based grouping method, was selected to perform this task, based on the rationale that motorbikes should pass

Fig. 1. Example where the start and end of a track are not the same depot

from the depots more frequently than any other locations. However, for parcel delivery, the analysis shows that many motorbikes do not return to the depot as much as the food delivery motorbikes do, as shown in Figure 2. Moreover, from day to day, the stops that these motorbikes visit are very similar. Therefore, it was demonstrated that the density of points was not a valid criterion.

Fig. 2. Example of a full-day trip, where the vehicle only returns to the depot at the end of the day.

Therefore, the procedure to identify the location of depots for each service type is as follows (as a ground-truth, locations of well-known delivery offices were obtained from OpenStreetMap data):

- For food services, the DBSCAN algorithm is applied for each vehicle. The parameters that have been used are $\text{eps} = 0.02$ m and $\text{min_sample} = 20$. These are values set experimentally, seeing that it runs fast and that the results are good. The points that are entered into DBSCAN are points that are 5 hours followed by a random day. If, when applying the DBSCAN

algorithm, it is able to differentiate more than one cluster, the centroid of the cluster is calculated and this is the depot assigned to the vehicle. Otherwise, the DBSCAN algorithm is applied again using data from another day.

- For parcel delivery, the algorithm iterates over all the vehicles, and all the data for each vehicle is saved but differentiated by day. In this way, a centroid is calculated with the first data of each day and another centroid with the last data of each day. This is done because it has been seen that motorcycles often leave and arrive at the same place. Calculating the distances of the two centroids, the maximum distance has generally turned out to be very small, and in most cases the two centroids are very close, which would indicate that it reflects a DEPOT. Each vehicle is assigned the centroid calculated with the first points of each day.

3.3 Trip model and statistics

Once the depot locations are obtained, consecutive tracks are joined and then divided every time a visit to a depot is detected, obtaining a set of circular trips.

For HDFE services, the duration and speed of these trips have a very skewed distribution to the left, having an average of $t = 25.69$ minutes for the duration and $d = 4.14$ kilometres for the distance travelled. The delivery time windows for an acceptable quality of service specified by the food companies are unknown but the duration statistics can be used to model them. For HDPE services, the distribution is more balanced, but there are many outliers that have a very high value for the duration and length of the trip, while their means are $t = 206.60$ minutes and $d = 21.53$ kilometres, respectively. To filter this data, it has been decided to use a variable that relates duration and length: average speed (speed = duration/length). Its distribution is also a little skewed by outliers. The data is filtered according to speed values so that a more centred distribution of the three variables is obtained.

For HDFE, values that are above the 97th quantile in speed have been discarded. So that there are no values with the speed very close to 0, values below quantile 1 have been discarded. For HDPE, values with $d = 0$ are discarded. In this case, the values that are within the 1st and 92nd quantile are selected. By doing this cleaning, almost 7% of the data is lost. Furthermore, the quartiles have not changed much, while the maximums have decreased considerably.

3.4 Battery consumption vs. trip relation modelling

Each battery SoC data is associated to a geographic location in the trip (the trip-points) corresponding to the same motorbike, according to the timestamp. Then, trip-points are grouped into short-distance segments using a random 500m-1000m segment size. These segments will be the basis of the training model. For each segment, we calculate the following: elevation difference between the start and end point locations, distance of the segment, SoC deviation from start point to the end point, as well as the average speed limit of the road between the points of the segment according to OpenStreetMap.

4 Application use case

Two main modules will be built after applying the procedure presented above: 1) the Route Planning module and 2) the Battery Consumption and Fleet Behavior module. In each process, multiple combinations constructed as the combination of potential locations and sizes will be built. In a third stage, the KPIs obtained from the aggregations of journeys and charging stations usage are computed.

The objective of the Route Planning module is to create a series of user requests, consisting of a pair of origin-destination and origin datetime, and to assign motorbikes to serve sequences of requests. Since parcel and food delivery journey tracks are available and have been modelled according to the previous section, machine learning models can be built to create the user requests. The stops contained in each trip refer to a user request. Each stop is therefore associated with the census section identifier according to a point-to-polygon map-matching relation, so that the aggregated demand (sum of stops) each day is translated into a set of socio-economic indicators by timeframe, and delivery type, indicating day of week, holiday or not, weather type and temperature.

Once the demand is created, the Battery Consumption and Fleet Behaviour module is aimed at estimating the battery consumption of each motorbike due to the route assignments. In addition, this module will need to evaluate energy consumption and cost due to the selected charging strategy.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented the battery consumption and route planning modelling considerations for food and parcel delivery through the use of a fleet of electric motorbikes. The presented work is part of the ongoing process to build a charging station location and dimensioning tool for electric motorbikes through a digital twin. Sizing electric motorbikes fleet and their associated charging station infrastructure, opens multiple optimisation problems. In this context the analysis of the challenges presented by a real-life dataset and the processes required to prepare the data before the creation of the models have been presented.

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